

BEST AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES TO HARVEST CEREAL CHAFF

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ABSTRACT: This work has been developed under the AGROinLOG Project, “Demonstration of innovative integrated biomass logistics centres for the Agro-industry sector in Europe”. An Integrated Biomass Logistics Center (IBLC), is based on the introduction of new production chains into existing agro-industries by using new biomass feedstock. The AGROinLOG Project dedicates great attention to investigate the potential of cereal chaff as a valuable resource. Made up of glumes, seed husk and rachis, it is valuable for animal feed or litter, or as feedstock for energy purposes. During cereal threshing, it is commonly left on the ground together with other thinner part of the cereal stems, whole or cracked kernels and weed seeds. Due to its value, many machineries builders has recently developed several systems for its recovery. The study represents a detailed and accurate survey of the harvesting technologies available at present in the market.

Keywords: threshing residues, combine harvester, straw baling, weed seeds, bioenergy

1 INTRODUCTION

The development of bio-economy has increased the biomass demand. Consequently, there is a competition for biomass utilization for food, feed, chemical and energy purposes [1]. The European policy for energy encourages the utilization of agro-forestry residues, limiting the energy crops plantations [2,3]. In this scenario, it is crucial to exploit the potential of biomass resources that are currently unexploited [4].

Among the agricultural residues, cereal chaff has gained interest due to their availability and properties both for energy purposes and for animal feeding [5, 6]. Moreover, from agronomic point of view, the collection of the chaff reduces the weed seed stock in the soil avoiding the herbicide treatments [7].

According to European yearly grain production, more than 50 Mt of chaff could be collected [8]. However, such resource is generally left on the ground after cereal threshing.

During the seed cleaning in the combine harvester, the chaff together with other fine residues (such as, short straw, damaged seeds and weed seeds) is retained by the sieves underneath the straw walkers and is blown to the rear of the combine.

Usually, this material is simply left to fall on the ground, and covered by the straw. The layer in direct contact with the ground cannot be collected with the pick-up in the following baling operation.

However, the growing interest in the exploitation of these residues both for energy (combustion, biogas) and for animal husbandry (fodder, litter), and also the need to reduce the load of seeds of resistant weeds (in the case of organic farming), has pushed some constructors to develop systems for the recovery of the chaff, separately or together with the straw.

The present review shows the main chaff collection technologies available on the market that, basically, implement the following mechanical chains:

- Chaff discharged on the top or inside of the straw swath for baling all together in a second time.
- Chaff discharged to an integrated back container, while straw can be both baled or spread on the ground.
- Chaff discharged to a towed trailer or no-stop baler.

The first method of collection can be preferred when biomass is used for energy production. In fact, baling the

straw and chaff together, increases the amount of total biomass collected per hectare and the bales density [9].

On the other hand, collecting chaff separately from straw allows to obtain a product with an higher nutritive value than straw, suitable for husbandry feeding.

2 AVAILABILITY AND CHARACTERISTICS OF CEREAL CHAFF

Chaff is made up of seed glumes, seed husk and rachis (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Wheat chaff

During cereal threshing, the chaff is normally dispersed in the field together with straw and other fine residues retained by the combine sieves, such as unthreshed heads, short straw, leaf material, weed seeds and whole or cracked kernels from the harvested crop.

This material can be estimated in about 7% of the threshed product (40% are seeds, 48% straw, 5% stubble) (Figure 2).

According to EUROSTAT, more than 300 Mt grain is harvested yearly in EU28 [10] and considering a mean chaff to grain ratio of 0.17, more than 52 Mt yr⁻¹ could be available to be collected in Europe [8].

Figure 2: Material balance of cereal harvesting

3 MECHANICAL SOLUTIONS FOR CHAFF RECOVERING

Currently, several solutions for chaff harvesting are available on the market, and other are still at prototype stage. Conceptually, they are based on two management methods:

- collection of chaff together with straw;
- collection of chaff separately from straw.

In the first case, the chaff is discharged either above the straw swath or inside it, in order to be recovered in a second time by a baler together with the straw, increasing by 20-25% the total biomass collected.

In the separate collection, the chaff is delivered to dedicated collection systems, such as trailers towed by a tractor or by the combine itself, integrated containers in the rear of the combine, non-stop baling systems.

Both management methods implement different chaff delivery systems, including: augers, blowers, conveyor belts. The combination of management methods and delivery systems determine different mechanical solutions that can be summarized as following:

1. Windrowing systems
2. Blower systems
3. Systems with conveyor belt and chaff cart
4. Dedicated back container systems
5. One pass harvest and baling systems
6. Modified chaff spreader systems

3.1 Windrowing systems

The windrowing systems, preferred when using large harvesting heads, consist of kit mounted in the rear part of the combine harvester. It provides the collection of the chaff directly from the sieves, the lifting of the material by means of a augers system, followed by the releasing on the top of the windrow. In this way, the chaff forming a layer on the straw swath can be baled together with it, avoiding any contact with the ground.

The French manufacturer Thierart (1) proposes two types of kit based on this principle, to be applied to different models of combine harvesters. With the kit specifically developed for the New Holland CR combine, the chaff is discharged on the straw windrow through a slide (Figure 3), while for other brand, through a removable hatch (Figure 4).

As an alternative to the recovery of the chaff, both kit foresee the evenly spreading of the chaff on the field for its following burying. In the first case, by lifting the slide and conveying the chaff towards the ventilation system, while in the second by activating a hydraulic deflector placed under the hatch.

Figure 3: Thierart windrowing system for NH CR combine and schematic representation

Figure 4: Thierart windrowing system for Claas Lexion combine and schematic representation

3.2 Blower systems

In these systems, the convey and delivery of chaff is provided by a combination of augers and turbines. A hopper placed under the sieves collects the chaff while an horizontal auger inside transports the material to the turbine. Then, the hydraulically driven turbine generates the cyclone for the expulsion of the material (Figure 5).

The French manufacturers Thierart and Thievin (2) adopt such system with varying commercial proposals.

The basic solution foresees the discharging of the product over the swath. Like in the windrowing systems, the chaff can be successively baled together with the straw. Otherwise, through the application of a rigid PVC pipe, the product can be sent inside a trailer, while the straw is windrowed or spread on the ground.

The trailer can be towed by a tractor moving in a lateral side, or by the combine itself (solution adopted by the partnership between the French manufacturers Thievin and Agri-structures) (Figure 6).

Also in this case, the option for spreading chaff on the ground is provided. This solution consists in applying at the turbine a "V" shaped spreader instead of the PVC pipe: the chaff thrown at high speed against the spreader is dispersed uniformly on both sides.

Figure 5: Thievin turbine system with discharge on windrow and schematic representation

Figure 6: Thievin turbine system with discharge on a trailer towed by a tractor (up) and by the combine itself

The Canadian Redekop (3) and the Australian Trufab (4) manufacturers, propose a chaff blower combined with a cyclone. The chaff blower is the same blower used to blow chaff into trailing wagons. The system adds a cyclone at the end of the blower to drop chaff directly on the straw windrow, allowing the baling with the straw.

The cyclone reduces the air pressure, allowing the chaff to fall.

Figure 7: Trufab chaff cyclone and blower for transferring chaff to the top of the straw windrow

3.3 Systems with conveyor belt and chaff cart

Chaff carts are widely adopted among the Australian “Harvest weed seed control” (HWSC) practices. The carts, towed by the combine harvester, collect chaff and weed seeds escaping the harvester. In recent years the chaff delivery system changed from cross augers and blowers to a simple conveyor belt (Figure 8).

The conveyor belt system has proven to be more efficient compared to traditional chaff transfer systems requiring less power from the header.

It is possible to collect all of the material that comes out of the back of the combine harvester or spread the straw and just catch the chaff coming from the sieves.

Figure 8: Springfield Chaff Cart

3.4 Dedicated back container systems

The French manufacturers Thierart and Bionalan (5) produce dedicated containers to be applied on the combine harvesters of different brand. The system consists of a collection container, placed behind the combine harvester, capable to be filled with chaff, while straw is discharged on the ground. The structure can be rigid but heavier or made of tarpaulin inside a metal chassis.

During the harvesting, the chaff fall into an hopper at the exit of the combine harvester and then transferred by means of two vertical screws in the dedicated box. Once filled, the residues are discharged at the edge of the field to be collected at a later time by a baler (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Bionalan back container and schematic representation

3.5 One pass harvest and baling systems

This system allows to harvest and bale the residues in one pass, avoiding the contact with the ground.

Thierart provides an interesting option that foresees the continuous pressing of the only chaff, simultaneously to the threshing (Figure 10). It consists of a modular system, made of a round baler connected to a 2 m³ tank and a dedicated power system, towed by the combine harvester.

Figure 10: Thierart modular system for continuous pressing of the chaff during threshing

Similarly, the French company Perard (6) has developed a baling system for chaff, named VMP.

Connected laterally to a combine harvester, the VMP sucks out the compressed chaff in the form of cylindrical boots 20 times denser. The system, still in the prototype stage, is automated with a control console in the combine harvester's cab and has its own power source from an integrated diesel engine.

Figure 11: Perard VPM system

Hillco Technologies (7), has developed a single pass baling system for straw and all other threshing residues.

The materials from the rear of the combine are blown into a hopper which is attached to the front of a standard John Deere round baler (Fig. 12).

Figure 12: Hillco Single Pass Round Bale System for John Deere

The Australian Glenvar (8) sells the Bale Direct System which provides single-pass harvest and baling of threshing residues using a large square baler linked directly to the combine by a drawbar attached to the main front drive axle. Residue from the combine is fed directly into baler via a conveyor belt. The power to drive the baler comes from a hydraulic pump mounted on the combine.

Figure 13: Glenvar Bale Direct System

3.6 Modified chaff spreader systems

The Swedish manufacturer Rekordverken (9) has developed a system, named "Combi", that allows the management of straw and chaff together or separately, through the spreading in the field or the recovery of the two products. In fact, the chaff spreader can be adjusted to throw alternatively the chaff on the combine sides or towards the straw chopper. Then, by activating or deactivating the straw chopper, four combinations in total are obtainable as follows:

- Straw chopper deactivated / chaff spreader in admixing mode: unloading of the straw in the swath for the subsequent baling together with the chaff, which is thrown by the chaff spreader into the straw flow (Fig. 14A);
- Straw chopper deactivated / chaff spreader in spreading mode: the straw is windrowed but chaff is spread over the entire working width of the machine instead of be mixed into the straw flow (Fig. 14B).

- Straw chopper activated / chaff spreader in admixing mode: straw and chaff go together inside the straw chopper and are spread over the entire working width of the machine. (Fig. 14C).

Straw chopper activated / chaff spreader in spreading mode: straw is chopped and spread and chaff is spread separately over the entire width of the machine (Fig. 14D).

The first combination, preferred for energy purposes, has the objective of maximizing the quantity of material to be baling. The second one is chosen in order to collect less dusty straw as bedding material (straw without chaff).

The third distribution option allow to chop all residues together distributing the mixed organic matter to the ground.

The last option guarantees the separate management of the two residues and avoids overloading the straw chopper.

Figure 14: Four combinations for the Rekordverken Comby System

4 CONCLUSIONS

The survey, though accurate, has revealed the existence of a limited number of manufacturers that offer mechanical solutions for the recovery of the chaff (Table II).

In general, the solutions that provide for the discharge on the swath (windrowing system or turbine system) or inside it (modified chaff spreader), have a limited investment cost, are easily adaptable to all types of combine harvester and they don't influence the harvesting performance (working time). On the other hand, the collection of the chaff together with the straw offers fewer options for its exploitation, mainly energy production.

On the contrary, the separate collection allows a greater range of possible destinations for chaff and straw. However, in systems that use trailers for chaff recovery (turbine systems with trailer and chaff-cart) and in one pass harvest and baling systems, the less manoeuvrability, has a negative effect on working time. Moreover, these solutions are more expensive. Pros and cons of each technology are showed in the Table I.

Table I: Pros and cons of each technology analysed

System	Pros	Cons
Windrowing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Harvester performance unmodified - Adaptability to all models of combine - Low investment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Valorisation of chaff mainly for energy - Possible chaff losing in raining conditions
Turbine / discharging on the swath	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Harvester performance unmodified - Adaptability to all models of combine - Low investment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Valorisation of chaff mainly for energy - A hydraulic adaptation is required - Possible chaff losing in raining conditions
Turbine / discharging on a trailer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The separate collection allows a greater range of possible valorisation for chaff and straw 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Worst manoeuvrability - Risk of clogging (pipe) in raining conditions - PVC pipe wear
Conveyor belt and chaff cart	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Less energy consumption comparing to auger and turbine delivery systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possible chaff losing in windy conditions (the goal is the collection of seed weeds)
Dedicated back container	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adaptability to all models of combine - High collection of seed weeds -Autonomy (discharging at field-edge) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher costs - Overhang and weight on the rear axle - Risk of dirt under piles
One pass harvest and baling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overall working time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High costs
Modified chaff spreader	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Harvester performance unmodified - Little extra maintenance - Original manufacturer's equipment - Ease to activate / deactivate the system - Low investment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No separate collection - Possible chaff losing

Table II: List of the manufacturers mentioned in this survey and their solutions

Manufacturer	Collection of chaff together with straw	Separate collection
Thierart	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chaff on the swath (chutes/hatch/turbine) One pass harvest and baling (turbine) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chaff into <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - towed trailers (turbine) - back containers (auger systems)
Thievin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chaff on the swath (turbine) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chaff into towed trailers (turbine)
Rekordverken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chaff inside the swath (modified chaff spreader) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None
Redekop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chaff on the swath (blower combined with a cyclone) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chaff into trailers (blowers)

Trufab	Chaff on the swath (blower combined with a cyclone)	Into chaff carts (blower / conveyor belt)
Bionalan		Chaff into back containers (auger systems)
Springfield		Into chaff carts (conveyor belt)
Hillco	Single pass round baling (blower)	
Glenvar	Single pass square baling (conveyor belt)	
Perard		Single pass baling (blower)

5 NOTES

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- (2) <http://www.remorques-agricoles.fr/turbopaille-recuperateur-menues-pailles>
- (3) <http://www.strawchopper.com/>
- (4) <http://www.trufab.com.au/chaff-carts.html>
- (5) <https://www.bionalan.fr/nos-produits/recuperateur-de-menue-paille>
- (6) <https://www.perard.fr>
- (7) <http://www.hillcotechnologies.com/sprb-systems.html>
- (8) <http://www.glenvarbaledirect.com.au/>
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8 LOGO SPACE

